

The importance of cartoons in English Language Teaching Process

Solijonova Orzuxon Salimjon qizi

English Philology Language Teaching

Fergana State University

solijonovaorzuxon17@gmail.com

Annotation: English is the language which is mostly used in tourism, travel, science and technology. In this regards claims that this important role of English has greatly contributed to the movement of teaching English as a foreign language. Therefore, nowadays more and more attention is being given to teach this language. In this process, cartoons may seem as a childish activity, but they have a huge impact in terms of learning English. In this article, the significance of them are proved.

Introduction: Today, English language is one of the most widely learnt and spoken language around the world. It is also used in communication between nations in business. Moreover, many scientific books are written in English and the teaching of English has become a necessity in many countries of the world. In spite of this, a great number of students are unable to use effectively and communicate fluently in English language after many years of English study in secondary schools. There are so many solutions to deal with this problem. Among these, watching cartoons is the most effective way to manage language learning.

A cartoon is a film, movie or a small video with animation in it or a simple drawing of things that we see around us in an entertaining way with plenty of colorful characters in it. They are intended to perform for children in order to be full of joy and make them happy. They are usually printed in newspapers, comic books and magazines or they are broadcasted on the television. Previously, cartoons were only aimed at giving pleasure and enjoyment to kids. However, nowadays they are extensively used for other purposes as well especially, in education.

Teaching profession demands to be patient and it is very tough. It takes a lot of effort to transfer the whole lot of information from your own mind into someone else's mind. That is why, it involves lots of new methods, innovative technologies and ideas that make it easier. Animated films have already been the best assistant for long times. With the help of them, students can understand easier and experience more.

In the conventional teaching methodology, knowledge was imparted to the students by means of a systematic conversation or a discussion. But the upcoming generation is a bit different. The new generation of children wants to scrutinize almost everything. With so

many queries popping in children's mind, the conventional scheme of teaching flops. This presents the need for new techniques for teaching. Sometimes, this is achieved through the use of cartoons or comic strips. Cartoons have proven themselves to be very advantageous for educating children. From the very beginning, they have been conveying moral values.

Now there are reasons why we consider cartoons as an essential tool in education.

•**Cartoons can catch Attention:** Children are pure creatures of the world, hence they always want to enjoy every moment of their life. They have naturally got desire to cheer up all the time wherever they go, whatever they do. And it is human nature to correlate cartoons with fun and humour. Therefore, it can be said that in search for entertainment the first entity around them which will seek student's attention will be cartoons or comic strips. Not only children, but even adults also do the same.

•**Cartoons can lead to better understanding:** All we know, there are some kind of theoretical matters that can not be understood. In order to explain them, some real-life examples or practical experiences are needed.

•**Cartoons can reduce fear of public speaking:** A cartoon comic strip has a lot of characters in it with different individual dialogues. A teacher can assign each of the characters to the students and tell them to perform a play on the comic strip. This will boost the student's confidence. The students will get a chance to speak or perform in front of the whole class. It will enhance their speaking skills. It is beneficial for the rest of the students as well because they will understand the story in a better way. It will be like a fun session for everyone.

•**Cartoons can teach students about moral principles:** At school, it is not easy to teach pupils how to behave truly. Moral values and good manners are more important in society. Teachers are in charge of their pupils whether youngsters behave badly or properly everywhere. If instructors show constantly different kind of cartoons or videos, they will have ideas about how to deal with various strange situations. After that they do not face difficulties or they do not have dilemmas what to do. Because with the help of such animations, insisting on friendship, respecting each other, following own dreams or fighting for life are learnt.

•**Cartoons can improve creative skills:** After watching cartoons again and again, they will form some types their own cartoon characters. When you give an assignment about something imaginative, they can draw astonishing heroes, of course you will be surprised. It is the power of cartoons, is not it?!

•**Cartoons can enhance vocabulary box.** Cartoons have a positive effect on children's mind. While kids are watching animative videos, they listen to new unknown words, they learn gestures or voice tones and they find out the structure of sentence. Then they will begin imitate them. Their questions increase day by day, you will have to answer their

never-ending innocent questions. You even do not notice the improvement of your relationship.

•**Cartoons can make teachers lovely.** There are not children who do not like watching cartoons. That is why when teacher bring students a good cartoon, they never regret this. In this process, mutual trust, love, respect as well understanding become better.

Once these kind of relations develop, students will change the outlook about subject like boring, unnecessary and difficult. They will be more active towards lesson. They will not miss every word that is said by teacher. At the end, the result is positive that student-teacher bond sounds like perfect.

Watching cartoons with subtitles is a good way to learn language. You should not watch it without subtitles. Then you will have a chance to turn off them completely. Day by day, step by step you can! If teachers have a trouble in choosing a particular cartoon, there are so many animations that can help them language learning. Now we have the list of the best cartoons to learn English. Here they are:

Beginner:

•**World party.** The series was created by The Jim Henson Company from July 8, 2016 to March 2, 2021. Running time is 13 minutes. It consists of 3 seasons, 60 episodes. The vocabulary-building program features a group of five young animals, Kip the Wallaby, Bailey the Elephant, leader Franny the Cheetah, the mascot Lulu the Panda, and Tilly the Tortoise, "as they sing, dance and play". As the name suggests, this movie cartoon teaches about new words to the youngest viewers. In it, simple, everyday themes, communication styles are mentioned. Each character speaks clearly using different tones. Our kids can memorize English words and start using them in their own life.

•**Dora, The Explorer.** This is an American children's animated television series and multimedia franchise created by Chris Gifford, Valerie Walsh Valdes and Eric Weiner that premiered on Nickelodeon on August 14, 2000, and ended on August 9, 2019. One of the most simple cartoons to practise English is Dora, The Explorer. It focuses on a girl named Dora accompanied by a monkey known as Boots, as they go on adventures. There are plenty of reasons. Firstly, this is not confusing and so fast. Elementary level of kids can understand it. Secondly, during the animation she never stops asking feedback. At this time, learners can practise with answering the question not their language, in English. Thirdly, if you can not realize some words, you can pause and repeat and manage it!

•**Peppa Pig.** This cartoon can be very useful to differentiate British English and American English. Because Peppa's family and friends talk with each other in British English. Your pronunciation will be raised. Peppa Pig is a British preschool animated television series by Astley Baker Davies. The show follows Peppa, an anthropomorphic female piglet, and her family, as well as her peers portrayed as other animals.

Intermediate:

• **The Last Airbender** (sometimes it refers ATLA). This animation was produced between February 21, 2005 and July 19, 2008 consisted of 3 seasons, 61 series. The duration of every episode is 23 minutes that can keep audience amused. With this cartoon, pupils not only can learn new vocabulary, but also imitate characters. As a result, their speaking skills will be improved without realising it. By watching them constantly, teachers minimize their difficulties towards children.

• **Disenchantment**. This is for those who are fun of the Simpsons. It creates atmosphere which kids relax and feel its uniqueness. You should pay an attention to jokes told in it and realize the meaning of them.

Advanced:

• **Voltron, Legendary Defender**. It was remade, so watching this may make them feel quite nostalgic and remind of some nostalgic memories. Several friends confront a great mastery. As a result, some kind of alien creatures as well as large spaceships are discovered by them. You can enrich your vocabulary.

Conclusion:

Language is the most important factor in human life. Especially, in our era we have to know at least three or four foreign languages. Many learners find difficulty in English, however, animated films can make English easier. Teachers can use them anytime, of course, with purposes related to their themes. It can be pointed out they are harmless and have a crucial effect on kids' bringing-up. Demonstrating cartoons in classrooms should be implemented at schools enhancing moral values together language skills. They encourage children to be active and eager to learn new something, enjoy the class and take part in some kind of language competitions.

References:

1. <https://targetstudy.com/articles/importance-of-cartoons-in-teaching.html>
2. <https://teach.its.uiowa.edu/teaching-cartoons/teaching-cartoons-details-examples>
3. <https://oxfordlanguageclub.com/page/blog/7-of-the-best-cartoons-to-learn-english>
4. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Avatar:_The_Last_Airbender
5. <https://www.fluentu.com/blog/english/best-cartoons-for-learning-english/>
6. CARTOONS IN LANGUAGE TEACHING AND LEARNING. Ms. Sajana. C, Assistant Professor, Department of Science and Humanities (English), Sri Krishna College of Engineering and Technology.
7. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dora_the_Explorer